

Career Advancement and Participatory Decision Making of Teachers: Predictor on Job Satisfaction in Public Primary Schools in Nandi County, Kenya

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to investigate career advancement and Participatory decision making of the teachers by head teachers as a predictor of job satisfaction in public primary schools in Nandi County, Kenya. This study was guided by the following objectives: To determine the extent to which head teachers encourage Career advancement influence teachers' job satisfaction. To determine the extent to which participatory decision making by head teachers influence teachers job satisfaction. A descriptive research design was used. The study was anchored on two factor theory Herzberg-hygiene theory developed by Fredrick Herzberg (1968) and job characteristics Model by Hack man and Oldham (1980). The target population for the study was 691 head teachers and 5470 teachers in 691 primary schools. The total sample was 548 teachers. Multi-stage random technique and Simple random sampling were used. The data collection instruments were questionnaires. Validity was done through pilot study and content validity was used to check the representation of the research questions in the questionnaires. The reliability was tested using Pearson's Moment Co-efficient approach. The results from questionnaires were interpreted and analyzed using frequencies' percentages 'and means. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Qualitative data was analyzed using Analysis of Variance(ANOVA). The results shows that the null hypothesis H_01 was rejected which implies that there was a relationship between head teachers 'involvement in career advancement of teachers and teachers' job satisfaction. This implies that when head teachers 'involve teachers in career advancement the teachers feel encouraged and satisfied. Career advancement had an influence on teachers' job satisfaction. This shows participatory decision making by head teachers had some influence on teachers' job satisfaction. From the findings, results from testing of the null hypothesis H_02 . The null hypothesis H_02 was rejected which implies that there was a relationship between head teachers involving teachers in decision making and teachers' job satisfaction. This implies that when head teachers involve teachers in critical decision making in schools they feel part and parcel of well being of the school hence feel satisfied. They head teachers should recommend teachers for promotion and mobilize parents by involving Board of Management so as to get resources. The government through the ministry of education should: provide policies on Career advancement are effective and that it does not interfere with the teachers schedule in school. The Quality Assurance Service should ensure they act as key monitors' especially in supervision and encourage job satisfying practices through collaborative decision making. The government through the ministry of education should: Consider teachers are involved in decision making in school on matters education to ensure participation of all teachers is paramount in order to ensure that teachers are satisfied with their jobs.

KEYWORDS: Career advancement, Participatory decision making and job satisfaction.

1. BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

According to James & Hannah (2013), Job satisfaction is an important element in work situation and has been associated with increased a committed to the organization. Employee satisfaction has been an important issue for academicians and scholars. High levels of absenteeism and staff turnover has affected various organizations, very few organizations has made job satisfaction a top priority, because of failure to understand the significant opportunity that lies in front of them. Organization that create work environment that attract, motivate and retain hard-working individuals was better position to succeed in a competitive environment that demands quality and cost- efficiency. Kumari (2011), job Satisfaction is a set of favorable or unfavorable feelings and emotions with which employees view their work. A person with high level of job satisfaction holds positive feelings about the job, while a person who is dissatisfied with job holds negative feelings about the job. Job satisfaction is an important concern for both the employee as well as the employer as it has an impact on much organizational behavior

In more developed Countries, such as the United States of America USA, the United Kingdom and Australia teachers shows that satisfied teachers have a positive effect on classroom Learning. Plunkett and Dyson (2011) .Examining with educating and retaining new teachers in rural Australia; salaries, working conditions also play a critical role in determining the supply of qualified teachers and in influencing their decisions about remaining in the profession. Cohen and Aya (2010) job satisfaction has been a key factor for understanding occupational involvement and commitment. It is an overall perceptual response to and general attitude toward the current job. Bessel, Dicks and Kepner (2013) Stated that an individual should be provided with an enabling environment to perform and produce the desired results. The teacher being an instrument of this success requires the physical, psychological, economical and social comfort.

Teachers' professional advancement opportunities are being used by the head teachers to positively increase teachers' job satisfaction in public primary school. Mc Sekakubo, Lwanga, Ndiwalana,(2014),There is a positive relationship between employee motivation and job satisfaction . The results indicate that if employees are well motivated through, for example, fair promotions and just able salary differences, they will work more towards betterment of the organization. Mwei (2013) Very few schools, teachers were rated to be highly and moderately satisfied with the school motivation practices. The researcher concluded that where teacher motivation practices were provided adequately the teachers were satisfied with their job.

Hood, 2016) suggested that in England's case, there is a shortage of expert teachers in part due to a lack of incentives to participate in training and development. Moreover, it argued that much of the continuing professional development (CPD) undertaken is of poor quality, and the significant investment involved could be much better spent. Estimates in TALIS suggest that England's secondary school teachers tend not to rate very highly the development activity they experience. Mickle Wright et al. (2014) noted that, for most topics covered, a lower proportion than in high performing jurisdictions reported a moderate or large impact on their teaching.

Participation in decision making is highly desired for managing work groups and individuals working in a work group based environment. Since participation in matters and policies of the organization makes the employee feel a sense of belongingness towards the organization, their levels of behavioral outcomes are impacted. Most importantly, effective management of jobs by delegating power throughout all levels of hierarchy would produce positive results to influence group learning and group commitment of employees within a work group.

The managers of public sector undertakings should focus on participation by every potential employee in day-to-day work issues. In this manner, the managers would be able to tap the skills and knowledge of potential employees towards the effective functioning of the organization. The practice of participative management makes the employee feel empowered to be able to work efficiently and it enhances job satisfaction. Managers should clarify the role and processes of participation and ensure expectations of employees are realistic and equitable.

The effect of participatory decision making on employee satisfaction is very important in an organization.. The findings indicate that activity autonomy had an average high-quality relationship with job satisfaction while transformational management and employee empowerment had a strong fantastic courting with employee satisfaction. Pacheco and webber (2014) conducted study on participative decision making and job satisfaction.

Increasing teacher turnover rates and a subsequent shortage of qualified teachers is a growing concern internationally (European Commission, 2018; Ingersoll, 2017). Teacher turnover comprises interrelated notions of teacher migration and attrition, where migration describes teachers moving to other schools, Yet, even recruiting more teachers may not solve the turnover problem as long as large numbers of the new teachers will be leaving schools, discontent with their professional status and working environment (Ingersoll, 2017; Sutch, Darling-Hammond, & Carver-Thomas, 2016).According to Muinde, (2013) found that one of the signs of deteriorating conditions in an organization is low job satisfaction which leads to strikes, slowdowns, absenteeism and employees high turnover rate.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Management practice of head teachers is fundamental in achieving job satisfaction of teachers. While the role of teachers' work for student outcomes is widely recognized, Increasing teacher turnover rates and a subsequent shortage of qualified teachers is a growing concern internationally (European Commission, 2018; Ingersoll, 2017) However, regardless the type of turnover, there are always negative consequences for a particular school from which a teacher is departing. Ronfeldt, Loeb, and Wyckoff (2013) suggest a

disruptive impact of turnover beyond compositional changes in teacher quality, especially in schools with lack of career advancement and lack of participatory involvement in decision making of teachers by head teachers.

The Government, Stake holders and parents have encourages career advancement and provide participatory decision making of capacity building and seminars for teachers. These rewards and efforts have been done to teachers. Despite all the efforts by the government, stakeholders, Board of management and parents to reward career advancement some teachers have low morale in their work which makes to become less dissatisfied with their job. Therefore, teachers' turnover in Nandi County is experience due to job dissatisfaction. It is such a situation that prompted the researcher to conduct a study to establish the influence of head teacher's management practices on teachers' job satisfaction in public primary schools in Nandi County.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This study was guided by the following objectives.

- i. To determine the extent to which head teachers encourage career advancement influence teachers' job satisfaction in public primary schools.
- ii. To determine the extent to which participatory decision making by head teachers influence teachers job satisfaction on the public primary school

4. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The study was guided by the following research hypotheses:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between head teachers' encourage in career advancement of teachers and teachers' job satisfaction in public primary schools in Nandi County, Kenya

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between head teachers involvement teachers in decision making and teachers' job satisfaction in public primary schools in Nandi County, Kenya

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

Career development for lecturers is quite important because with a future career, they will have enthusiasm in implementing the tri dharma of higher education (Zacher et al., 2019). Feelings of pleasure and happiness can be felt by someone by getting a certain satisfaction. If satisfaction is obtained from within, of course there are factors that cause satisfaction. The lecturer satisfaction factor may be influenced by the compensation and career development received by private universities in Serang City, where based on the survey results, compensation and career development for lecturers in Serang City are still low.

Career Development has a broader scope in an effort to improve and increase knowledge, abilities, attitudes and personality traits to assume different or higher responsibilities within the organization (Kim, 2018). The development of Human Resources (HR) is an activity that must be carried out by companies so that their knowledge, abilities and skills are in accordance with the demands of the work they are doing (Dahl et al., 2013; Susanto et al., 2020). The existence of development activities, employees are expected to be able to improve and overcome deficiencies in carrying out their work better, in accordance with the development of science and technology used by the company. to assume different or higher responsibilities within the organization (Hapsari et al., 2021). According to Wang and Wanberg (2017), career development consists of two dimensions, namely, career management and career planning. Career management includes indicators of organizational policies, work performance, educational level, and regeneration. Meanwhile, career planning includes indicators of training, work experience, work relations, and self-development.

Participative Decision Making means employee participation in decision making. Both are used interchangeable in this paper. Employee Participation or Involvement is defined as a process of involving and empowering employees to use their input towards creating value and improving organizational productivity (Sofijanov & Chatleska, 2013). Employee Participation also means direct involvement or engagement of employees towards applying ideas, expertise, and efforts in solving organizational problems and achieving its goals or objectives. The term participation according to Bateman & Crant, (2011) include people's involvement in decision making processes, in implementing programs, their sharing in the benefits of development and involvement in efforts to evaluate. The concept of employee participation implies a practice, which gives workers greater opportunity to be involved in decision-making beyond the immediate boundaries of their jobs (Devi, 2009). Westhuizen (2010) defined employee participation as the totality of forms, that is direct or indirect involvement of individuals and groups to contribute to the decision making process.

Beardwell and Claydon (2007) defined employee participation as the distribution of power between employer and employee in decision making processes, either through direct or indirect involvement. In addition, employee participation also refers to employee involvement in decision making at the workplace.

This study was based on two factor theory Herzberg-hygiene theory develop by Fredrick Herzberg (1968) and job characteristic Model by Hack man and Oldham (1980). According to Herzberg, factors that make employees feel good about their work are different from factors that make them feel bad about their work. Thus the theory considers job satisfaction and dissatisfaction as independent phenomena.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

6.1 The research design

The descriptive survey research design was the best to use in this research because, it allows the researcher to describe characteristics of an individual or group as they really are. (Kothari 2011). The study applied descriptive research design. Questionnaire was used to collect the data.

6.2 Target Population

The study was targeting 691 public primary schools in Nandi County which comprises of 691 head teachers and 5470 teachers across 6 Sub-Counties from Nandi County, Kenya.

6.3 Sample Size and Sampling Procedures

Kombo and Tromp (2006) describe a sample as a set of respondents selected from a large population for observation and analysis and chosen in a systematic way. Table 1 presents the sample size of head teachers and teachers selected per Sub- County in Nandi -County.

Table 1: Samples of the Study

Sub-counties	Schools	Sampled Schools 17%	Head Teachers 17 %	Teachers	Teachers 10 % of 5470
Nandi East	93	16	16	726	73
Nandi Central	93	16	16	772	77
Nandi North	107	18	18	1116	112
Nandi South	143	24	24	979	98
Tinderet	124	21	21	842	84
Chesumei	131	22	22	1035	114
Total	691	117	117	5470	548
		Simple random sampling	Simple random Sampling		Simple random Sampling

There are 691 Public primary schools within six Sub-Counties in Nandi County. The researcher used Multi-Stage Random Sampling technique. The researcher used randomly sample to select some zones in the Sub- County. Once the zones have been selected the researcher was randomly select 17% of primary schools within the selected zones. The head teacher was taken from the sampled public primary schools. The researcher sampled 10% of the teachers to get 548. The researcher administered questionnaires to the head teachers and the teachers.. Simple random sampling ensured that each element within the assessable population has an equal chance of being selected.

6.4 Validity of the Instrument

Validity indicates the degree to which an instrument measures what it is supposed to measure that is the extent to which differences found in the measuring instrument reflect true differences among those who have been tested Kothari (2008). To test the validity of

the instruments, a preliminary pilot study was done by researcher on a small size of 6 head teachers, 10 teachers. The researcher pretested instrument in the primary schools in Nandi County (2021). Where the researcher administered questionnaires to head teachers and teachers, then the results obtained was analyzed for the effectiveness of the instrument used to collect the data. Pre-testing allowed the researcher to improve their validity as well as familiarize with data collection process. Content validity was used to check the representation of the research questions in the questionnaires. The items that were found inadequate were discarded while some were modified. Secondly the researcher sought assistance from the supervisor in order to help improve content validity of the instrument.

The purpose was to assist in determine the accurate and clarity of the instrument and the estimated time required to completing and returning of the questionnaires before embarking on the actual study. The content validity was used to ascertain the results from supervisors and the specialists from the Department of Educational Administration and Planning has been incorporated for expert judgement.

6.5 Reliability of the Instrument

Mugenda and Mugenda (2010) define reliability of the research instruments as it level of internal consistency over time. Reliability therefore means a research instrument gives consistent results or data after repeated trial. Reliability was tested through test – retest method. This technique involved administering the questionnaire twice within a period of two weeks to the same respondents. Then Pearson’s moment co-efficient approach was used to determine the co-efficient of correlation using the formula shown.

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

From the findings, to determined correlation coefficient for head teachers and teachers’ questionnaires were 0.82 and 0.84 respectively. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2010) a coefficient of 0.80 or more simply shows that there is high reliability of data. In this case the instruments used in data collection were deemed highly reliable

6.6 Data Collection Instruments

The researcher used questionnaires for head teacher and teachers. Questionnaire as tool for collecting data enables the researcher to obtain a large quantity of data in expensively from a wide range of participants sometimes spread extensively in a geographic space. The research instrument that was use by the researcher in this study include both closed and open ended questionnaire for both head teachers and teachers’.

6.9 Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis entails making sense of massive amount of data, reduces the volume of information and identities significant patterns and constructing a framework for communicating the evidence of what the data revealed (Best & Kahn, 2011). The results of the questionnaires were checked for completeness as preparation for analysis. Data was then coded and entered into the computer for analysis using statistical package for social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0 by encoding responses from questionnaires. The results from questionnaires from Head teachers and teachers produced were interpreted by quantitative analysis using Frequencies, percentages and means were used to report the data.

Both quantitative and qualitative data was analysed. Descriptive statistics analyses which include frequencies and percentages were used. The results obtained were presented using. Inferential statistics was used include the ANOVA to analyse hypotheses the influence of head teachers Career advancement and influence of teachers’ participatory decision making on job satisfaction.

7. DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATIONS AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Influence of head teachers encouragement on career advancement on teachers job satisfaction

To find out the influence of head teachers encouragement on Career advancement on teachers job satisfaction, the researcher sought to ask questions that were related to head teachers’ encouragement on Career advancement to teachers’ job satisfaction. Table 2 shows the responses from the influence of head teachers’ encouragement on Career advancement on teachers’ job satisfaction. Where SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, UN=Undecided, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree
Table 2 shows teachers response on Head teachers’ encouragement on Career advancement

Table 2. Teachers’ response on Head teachers’ encouragement on Career advancement

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean	Sd
Appreciate further studies	14	27	69	201	167	4.0	0.993
Advancement makes teachers better	9	23	29	189	228	4.26	0.912
Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction	28	19	38	205	188	4.05	1.076
Encourages promotion of teachers	46	47	39	159	177	3.80	1.295
The advancement is autonomy	32	42	113	209	82	3.56	1.081
Allowed salary increase	83	90	81	135	89	3.12	1.378
Average Mean						3.8	1.123

Table 2 shows majority 42.1% of teachers Agreed that they appreciate further studies while 34.9% Strongly Agreed and 5.6% Disagreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed with a mean of (M=4.00, SD=0.993) that Teachers are provided with a clearly spelt out task.

On Advancement makes teachers better Majority 39.5% Agreed while 47.7% Strongly Agreed and 6.1% were Undecided respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed with a mean of (M=4.26, SD=0.912) that the Advancement makes teachers better On Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction Majority 42.9% of the teachers Agreed while 39.3% Strongly Agreed and 7.9% were Undecided respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed with a mean of (M=4.06, SD=1.076) Agree that Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction

On Encourages promotion of teachers Majority 37.0% of the teachers Strongly Agreed while 35.4% Agreed and 9.8% Disagreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed with a mean of ((M=3.80, SD=1.295) that Encourages promotion of teachers

On The advancement is autonomy 43.7% of the teachers Agreed while 23.6% were Undecided and 17.2% Strongly Agreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents Strongly agreed with a mean of (M=3.56, SD=1.081) that The advancement is autonomy

On Allowed salary increase 28.2% of the teachers said Agree while 18.8% Strongly Disagreed and 18.6% Strongly Agreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed with a mean of (M=3.12, SD=1.378) that Allowed salary increase.

Table 3 shows head teachers responses on Head teachers encouragement on Career advancement where HD=Highly Dissatisfied, MD= Moderately Dissatisfied, SS=Slightly Satisfied, MS=Moderately Satisfied, HS=Highly Satisfied

Table 3. Head teachers’ response on teachers’ encouragement on career advancement

Statement	HD	MD	SS	MS	HS	Mean	Sd
Allowed teachers to further education	3	9	14	28	42	4.01	1.119
Advancement makes teachers better	0	5	13	31	47	4.25	0.883
Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction	0	10	12	35	39	4.07	0.976
Encourages promotion of teachers	2	4	17	20	30	4.23	1.021
The advancement is autonomy	2	9	20	38	27	3.82	1.016
Allowed salary increase	3	15	14	32	32	3.78	1.162
Average Mean						4.03	1.030

Table 3 shows majority 43.8% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied that they Appreciate further studies while 29.2% were Moderately Satisfied and 14.6% Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly Satisfied with a mean of (M=4.01, SD=1.119) that Teachers are provided with a clearly spelt out task.

On Advancement makes teachers better Majority 49.0% were Highly Satisfied while 32.3% were Moderately Satisfied and 13.5% were Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly Satisfied with a mean of (M=4.25, SD=0.883) that the Advancement makes teachers better

On Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction Majority 40.6% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied while 36.5% were Moderately Satisfied and 12.5% were Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly Satisfied with a mean of (M=4.07, SD=0.975) that Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction

On Encourages promotion of teachers Majority 55.2% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied while 20.8% were Moderately Satisfied and 17.7% Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly Satisfied with a mean of (M=4.23, SD=1.021) that Encourages promotion of teachers

On The advancement is autonomy 39.6% of the head teachers were Moderately Satisfied while 28.1% were Highly Satisfied and 20.8% Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Moderately Satisfied with a mean of (M=3.82, SD=1.016) that the advancement is autonomy

On Allowed salary increase 33.3% of the head teachers were Moderately and Highly Satisfied respectively while 15.6% was Moderately dissatisfied. This implies that majority of the respondents were both Moderately and Highly satisfied with a mean of (M=3.78, SD=1.163) that Allowed salary increase.

Table 4 shows the distribution of Head teachers' encouragement on Career advancement on job satisfaction

Table 4. Distribution of Head teachers' encouragement on Career advancement on job satisfaction

ANOVA			Sum	of	Mean		
			Squares	Df	Square	F	Sig.
Allowed teachers to further education	Between Groups		17.279	4	4.320	3.865	.006
	Within Groups		101.710	91	1.118		
	Total		118.990	95			
Advancement makes teachers better	Between Groups		9.873	4	2.468	3.503	.010
	Within Groups		64.127	91	.705		
	Total		74.000	95			
Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction	Between Groups		18.779	4	4.695	5.958	.000
	Within Groups		71.710	91	.788		
	Total		90.490	95			
Encourages promotion of teachers	Between Groups		6.468	4	1.617	1.591	.183
	Within Groups		92.490	91	1.016		
	Total		98.958	95			
The advancement is autonomy	Between Groups		15.305	4	3.826	4.211	.004
	Within Groups		82.685	91	.909		
	Total		97.990	95			
Allowed salary increase	Between Groups		11.041	4	2.760	2.140	.082
	Within Groups		117.365	91	1.290		
	Total		128.406	95			

Table 14 shows that there was a statistically significant difference between groups and within groups determined by one-way ANOVA (F(4,91) =5,958.10, p=.000), (F(4,91) =4.211 p=.004) . On Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction and The advancement is autonomy respectively. There was no significant difference between groups for: Encourages promotion of teachers

and on Allowed salary increase as results show above $(F(4,91) = 1.591, p = .183)$, $(F(4,91) = 2.140, p = .082)$ respectively. This shows that Head teachers encouragement on Career advancement had some influence on job satisfaction.

4.8: Influence of Participatory decision making by head teachers and teachers job satisfaction.

To find out the influence of Participatory decision making provided by head teachers on teachers’ job satisfaction, the researcher sought to ask questions that were related to Participatory decision making provided by the head-teachers to teachers’ job satisfaction. Table 5 shows the responses from the influence of head teachers’ Participatory decision making on job satisfaction. Where SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, UN=Undecided, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree
Table 5 shows teachers’ response on participatory decision making by head teachers

Table 5. Teachers’ response on participatory decision making by head teachers

Statement	SD F	D F	N f	A f	SA f	Mean	Sd
Head teachers consults teachers in preparation of school budget	107	81	34	146	110	3.15	1.508
Head teachers involved teachers in subject allocation	89	113	59	139	78	3.62	1.423
Head teachers involves teachers in school purchases	83	143	51	134	67	3.14	1.483
Head teacher involves teachers in ordering for school instructional materials	85	66	90	149	88	3.49	1.420
Head teacher involves teachers in admitting new pupils	34	32	37	209	166	3.24	1.452
Head teachers involving teachers in drawing the strategic plan of the school	28	81	34	206	129	3.32	1.379
Head teacher involves teachers in recruitment of support staff	51	132	74	148	73	3.18	1.513
Head teacher involves teachers when dealing with discipline cases	27	56	38	180	177	3.89	1.190
Average Mean						3.38	1.421

Table 5 shows majority 30.5% of teachers Agreed that Head teachers consults teachers in preparation of school budget while 23.0% Strongly Agreed and 22.4% Strongly Disagreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed with a mean of $(M=3.15, SD=1.508)$ that Head teachers consults teachers in preparation of school budget.

On Head teachers involved teachers in subject allocation Majority 35.4% Strongly Agreed while 32.2% Agreed and 13.8% Disagreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents Strongly Agreed with a mean of $(M=3.62, SD=1.423)$ that they are Head teachers involved teachers in subject allocation.

On Head teachers involves teachers in school purchases Majority 29.3% of the teachers Agreed while 22.4% Strongly Agreed and 21.1% Strongly Disagreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents Agreed with a mean of $(M=3.14, SD=1.483)$ that Head teachers involves teachers in school purchases.

On Head teacher involves teachers in ordering for school instructional materials Majority 31.8% of the teachers Agreed while 29.7% Strongly Agreed and 16.5% Strongly Disagreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed with a mean of ((M=3.49, SD=1.420) that Head teacher involves teachers in ordering for school instructional materials.

Head teacher involves teachers in admitting new pupils majority 36.2% of the teachers Agreed while 21.1% strongly Disagreed and 20.9% Strongly Agreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents Agreed with a mean of (M=3.24, SD=1.452) that Head teacher involves teachers in admitting new pupils.

On Head teachers involving teachers in drawing the strategic plan of the school 40.4% of the teachers said Agree while 19.9% Strongly Agreed and 16.3% Strongly Disagreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents Agreed with a mean of (M=3.32, SD=1.379) that Head teachers involving teachers in drawing the strategic plan of the school.

On Head teacher involves teachers in recruitment of support staff 31.2% of the teachers Agreed while 23.4% Strongly Agreed and 23.2% Strongly Disagreed were respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents Agreed with a mean of (M=3.18, SD=1.513) that Head teacher involves teachers in recruitment of support staff

On Head teacher involves teachers when dealing with discipline cases 37.7% of the teachers Agreed while 37.0% Strongly Agreed and 11.7% Disagreed respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents Agreed with a mean of (M=3.89, SD=1.190) that Head teacher involves teachers when dealing with discipline cases.

Table 6 shows head teachers responses on participatory decision making of head teachers

where HD=Highly Dissatisfied, MD= Moderately Dissatisfied, SS=Slightly Satisfied, MS=Moderately Satisfied, HS=Highly Satisfied

Table 6. Head teachers' responses on participatory decision making of teachers

Statement	HD f	MD f	SS f	MS f	HS f	Mean	Sd
Consults teachers in preparation of school budget	5	8	23	29	31	3.93	1.172
Involves teachers in subject allocation	2	2	21	36	35	3.77	1.090
Engage teachers in school purchases	3	1	4	36	52	3.39	1.333
Consults teachers in ordering for school instructional materials	2	3	8	30	53	3.22	1.452
Involves teachers in admitting new pupils	4	5	9	36	42	3.75	1.076
Consult teachers in drawing the strategic plan of school	4	5	9	36	42	3.92	0.970
Engage teachers in recruitment of support staff	3	8	21	28	36	3.58	1.220
Involves teachers when dealing with discipline cases	3	4	6	28	55	3.94	0.971
Average Mean						3.69	1.161

Table 6 shows majority 32.3% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied that they Consults teachers in preparation of school budget while 30.2% were Moderately Satisfied and 24.0% Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly Satisfied with a mean of (M=3.76, SD=1.149) that Consults teachers in preparation of school budget

On Involves teachers in subject allocation Majority 37.5% were Moderately Satisfied while 36.5% were Highly Satisfied and 21.9% were Slightly Satisfied and Moderately dissatisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Moderately Satisfied with a mean of (M=4.45, SD=0.832) that Involves teachers in subject allocation.

On Engage teachers in school purchases Majority 54.2% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied while 37.5% were Moderately Satisfied and 4.2% Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly satisfied with a mean of (M=4.04, SD=0.928) that Engage teachers in school purchases.

On Consults teachers in ordering for school instructional materials Majority 55.2% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied while 31.3% were Moderately Satisfied and 8.3% Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly Satisfied with a mean of ((M=4.39, SD=0.875) that Consults teachers in ordering for school instructional materials

On Involves teachers in admitting new pupils majority 43.8% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied while 37.5% were Moderately Satisfied and 9.4% were Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly Satisfied with a mean of (M=4.34, SD=0.916) that Involves teachers in admitting new pupils.

On Consult teachers in drawing the strategic plan of school majority 43.8% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied while 37.5% were Moderately Satisfied and 9.4% Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly satisfied with a mean of (M=4.11, SD=1.055) that Consult teachers in drawing the strategic plan of school.

On Engage teachers in recruitment of support staff 37.5% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied while 29.2% were Moderately Satisfied and 21.9% Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were highly satisfied with a mean of (M=3.90, SD=1.100) that Engage teachers in recruitment of support staff.

On Involves teachers when dealing with discipline cases majority 57.3% of the head teachers were Highly Satisfied while 29.2% were Moderately Satisfied and 6.3% were Slightly Satisfied respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents were Highly satisfied with a mean of (M=4.33, SD=0.991) that Involves teachers when dealing with discipline cases.

8. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

8.1 Summary of the Study

The study investigated the influence of head teachers’ career advancement and participatory decision making on job satisfaction among teachers in public primary schools in Nandi County, Kenya.

The target population included 691 public primary schools which comprised of 691 head teachers and 5470 teachers across 6 Sub-Counties from Nandi County, Kenya. Simple random sampling was used to select 117 schools, 117 Head teachers and 548 teachers. Questionnaires were used as instruments for data collection for the study which had opened ended and closed ended questions. A pilot study was conducted in 6 schools to determine instrument validity of the questionnaires. Tests re-test method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. From the findings, the determined co-relation co-efficient for teachers and head teachers were 0.725 and 0.743 respectively. Therefore, the instruments used in data collection were deemed highly reliable. Data collected was both quantitative and qualitative in nature. Statistical package for social sciences was used for effective analysis of data.

Descriptive data analysis statistics such as percentage means, frequencies and standard deviation while inferential statistics was analysed using ANOVA test

The mean was used as the most efficient measure of central tendency.

Table 7 shows the hypothesis findings, test results and interpretation

Table 7. Hypothesis findings, test results and interpretations

Objectives	Respondents	Hypothesis Test	Test finding	Reference Tables	Interpretation
To determine the extent to which head teachers encourage Career advancement influence teachers’ job satisfaction	Head teachers	ANOVA	There was a statistically significant difference between groups as determined by one-way ANOVA (F(4,91) =5,958.10, p=.000), (F(4,91) =4.211 p=.004) for Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction and The advancement is autonomy respectively.	Table 14	Head teachers encouragement on Career advancement had some influence on teachers’ job satisfaction.

Table 7 shows the results from testing of the null hypothesis H_{01} was rejected which implies that there was a relationship between head teachers 'involvement in career advancement of teachers and teachers' job satisfaction. This implies that when head teachers involve teachers in career advancement the teachers feel encouraged and satisfied.

Questionnaires were used as instruments for data collection for the study which had opened ended and closed ended questions. A pilot study was conducted in 6 schools to determine instrument validity of the questionnaires. Tests re-test method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. From the findings, the determined co-relation co-efficient for teachers and head teachers were 0.725 and 0.743 respectively. Therefore, the instruments used in data collection were deemed highly reliable. Data collected was both quantitative and qualitative in nature. Statistical package for social sciences was used for effective analysis of data. Descriptive data analysis statistics such as percentage means, frequencies and standard deviation while inferential statistics was analysed using ANOVA test.

Table 8. Hypothesis findings, test results and interpretations

Objective	Respondents	Hypothesis Test	Test finding	Reference Tables	Interpretation
To determine the extent to which participatory decision making by head teachers influence teachers job satisfaction	Head teachers	ANOVA	There was a statistically significant difference between groups as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(4,91) = 5.642, p = .000$), ($F(4,91) = 4.198, p = .004$) and ($F(4,91) = 3.848, p = .006$) for Consult teachers in drawing the strategic plan of school, Consults teachers in ordering for school instructional materials and Consults teachers in preparation of school budget respectively.	Table 20	This shows participatory decision making by head teachers had some influence on teachers' job satisfaction.

The null hypothesis H_{02} was rejected which implies that there was a relationship between head teachers involving teachers in decision making and teachers' job satisfaction. This implies that when head teachers involve teachers in critical decision making in schools they feel part and parcel of well being of the school hence feel satisfied.

9. CONCLUSION

From the findings, the study concluded that head teachers encourage Career advancement influence teachers' job satisfaction and it was found that head teachers Career advancement had an influence on teachers' job satisfaction. It was evident by for Potential for opportunities enhance job satisfaction and the advancement is autonomy respectively. This implies that the more head teachers encourage career advancement the more teachers are satisfied with their jobs.

From the findings, the study concluded that participatory decision making provided by the head teachers influenced teachers' job satisfaction. This was evident by Consult teachers in drawing the strategic plan of school, Consults teachers in ordering for school instructional materials and Consults teachers in preparation of school budget respectively. This implies that the more head teachers involved teachers in participatory decision making on school matters the more they were satisfied with their jobs.

10. RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations made from the study are

1. Head teachers should use a variety of management practices to improve teachers' job satisfaction. They should also recommend teachers for promotion and mobilize parents by involving Board of Management so as to get resources.
- 2) The government through the ministry of education should: provide policies on Career advancement are effective and that it does not interfere with the teachers schedule in school

- 3) The Quality Assurance Service should ensure they act as key monitors' especially in supervision and encourage job satisfying practices through collaborative decision making.
- 4) The government through the ministry of education should: Consider teachers are involved in decision making in school on matters education to ensure participation of all teachers is paramount in order to ensure that teachers are satisfied with their jobs.
- 5) Ensure every teacher and employee share certain task or responsibility so that they feel they are contributing towards the success of the school. Through participation in decision making, principals can ensure that teachers are satisfied and they learn within work group.
- 6) There is need to carry out a research on Reasons as to why stakeholders in the education sector (TSC, MOE, principals and head teachers) do not fully involve teachers in decision making.

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